

The Study of Culture impacts on Male Managers' Decision Making within Multinational Project Teams; Case Study: Zirsakht Telecommunication Co

Corresponding Author: Seyed Farzad Mirmiran¹, Ali Sanayei^{*1, 2}

drmirmiran@yahoo.com

1 Department of Management, Najafabad Branch, Islamic Azad University, Najafabad, Iran

a_sanayei@ase.ui.ac.ir

2 Department of Management Research, Esfahan University, Esfahan, Iran

Abstract

The appropriate method for overcoming problems of new organizations is to provide knowledge based teams with optimum output. Making such teams needs experienced experts. Nowadays productive organizations are increasing and their developing depends on their globalization; therefore cultural differences may cause great changes in the decision making process in these teams.

The aim of the present study is to determine the influence of social culture on male managers' decision-making styles within multinational project teams. For this reason; the number of 100 person of senior and midlevel managers working in the project teams from the two company of Iranian Zirsakht Co and Korean KT Co through Available Non-probabilistic sampling method.

The influence of social culture on managers' decision-making styles has been examined through Structural Equation Model by using the software known as AMOS version 23 in the two section of Evaluation model Structural section. Also SPSS version 23 was applied for comparing analysis results.

The results of the recent study showed that social culture influences managers' decision making styles at international project teams from the two Iranian and Korean nationalities.

Keywords: Culture, Decision making Style, Multinational Project Teams, Managers

1. Introduction

Nowadays culture and its' impacts on organizations is one of important challenges on managers in different parts of the organization.

Culture can influence on different organization units such as; Human Resources, Manufacturing, R&D, Customer Relations, Marketing and in the macro levels it can influence managers' decision making style.

Furthermore developing international project teams have being developed during recent days. It means that foreign people with different culture, ideals and interests are being increased in the organization in the term of decision making.

Hence; the researcher has tried to explain circumstances of cultural effects on manager's decision making within multinational project teams for enabling managers to adopt appropriate strategies when confronting such cultural differences.

2. Statement of the Problem

Nowadays Globalization is the basis of business activities in the modern societies.

This phenomenon is something more than a vicissitude in the business area, but it is including a comprehensive social, cultural, political and economic approach. The influence of such vicissitude in the cultural area has caused huge revolutions inside of international organization (Bassam, 2013; pp 124, 125).

People with different nationalities have different cultures and they think and act different accordingly since culture is the basis of human character (Mirmiran, 2015; 3 Quoted from Ramadanian, 2011).

While middle and senior managers from different nationalities with different culture are working together in an international organization; diversity in decision making style is something unavoidable.

The role of culture in decision making has been studied 1976 by Barret and Bass for the first time and such studies have been developed through last two decades (Mirmiran, 2015:4).However for studies have been made on the quality area of culture impacts on managers' decision making style. On the other hand, developing international cooperation due to the globalization progress in developing countries has cause increase in the number international organization in the form of international project teams which is challenging for chief managers to integrate them in international project teams.

In Iran as a developing country; the subject of international project team increase is a very prevalent phenomenon in all industries therefore; according to the fact that there is no academic research in the mentioned in Iranian universities management research centers; the researcher is going to study of culture impacts in managers' decision making within multinational project teams.

3. Importance of the Research

The subject of culture diversity among nations is one of the main challenges of globalization in the recent world. We are living in the world that globalization means have affected every governments' administrative policies in the way of unifying them in the Global Village. (Mirmiran, 2013; 4, 5)

The prerequisite of such unification is developing necessary social, cultural, political, economic and industrial bases which is implying to gradual increase in the number of international organization and corporation. Such conditions is more intensive about developing countries.

Iran also as a developing country with geopolitical situation is including lots of international organizations and companies which are trying to level industries and substructures of the country with Globalization standards. In this regard; the government encourages developing knowledge based companies as one of the basis of resistive economy in Iran (Mirmiran, 2014; pp 5, 6). Since many of such companies are active in the area of technology exchange; they must organize international project teams within their organization.

Therefore it shows that Iranian organization managers may confront with increasing number of foreigners in their project teams and culture diversity will be their inevitable challenge at the decision making time. Thus it would be clear that controlling culture impacts on decision making style is crucial for the successful managers.

4. Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

4.1. Project Management

Projects are applied as a means for performing an organizational strategic plan usually. Project is a piece of planned work or an activity that is finished over a period of time and intended to achieve a particular purpose (Cambridge Dictionary). Projects are temporary activities during a period of time which leads to producing a unique product (PMBOK, 2000).

Project team includes group of people which collaborate with each other for achieving organizational goals (Mirmiran, 2015; pp 13, 14 quoted from Kohen & Baily, 2015). Taylor (2010) believes that project team contains an expert group who work with each other to perform a project.

Project teams constitute main body of the organization and organization success depends on the true selection of the project team members (Mirmiran, 2015; p 14 quoted from Sessa & Landon, 2011)

Project management is the application of systems and new managerial techniques in the way of project different steps' accomplishment which is contacting four stages of project definition, project planning, project performance and project accomplishment according to product life cycle (Mirmiran, 2015; p 17 quoted from Martin et al, 2014)

4.2. Culture

Hofstede (2005) defines culture as a joint planning which include thinking, feeling and mental acting between team members in which separate them from other group members. Culture is the characteristics and knowledge of a particular group of people, defined by everything from language, religion, cuisine, social habits, music and arts (Merriam Webster Dictionary)

Hofstede believe that culture is a kind of brain mental planning; so that each person has certain mental plans which is containing latent behavioral capabilities. These capabilities are achieved during life. Hofstede counts three mental planning include Personal layer, Joint layer and Universal layer. He has planned his cultural triple layer model as below.

Fig 1: Hofstede Cultural Triangle

Individual level deals with exclusive characteristics of mental planning for each person which is inborn to some extent. Culture joint layer deals with acquisitive characteristics of mental planning which is exclusive for each social group and

Universal layer deals with instinctive characteristics of mental planning which is common for all humanities (Mirmiran, 2015; p 18 quoted from Hofstede, 2005).

Therefore it is found that culture is a determinative factor in predicting personal treatment.

4.3. Decision Making

Decision Making is the most important part in the project implementation and it is one of main responsibilities of the business administrators. In fact each project is the series activities in connection with each other through with taken decisions (Mirmiran, 2015; 28 quoted from Neilson, 2001).

Decision making in groups may be defined as the method of combining certain preferences in a special social style in order to unify group favorite likes in the framework of certain decision (Mirmiran, 2015; p 31 quoted from Dabic, 2014).

Heretofore some important decision making models have been presented by management researchers such as Davies (1969), Vroon & Yetton (1973), Heraklius (1994) and etc. The most famous of decision making models is the Scott & Bruce (1995) model. According to Scott & Bruce; individual factors are the most crucial effective element in decision making. Therefore they have presented five decision making styles including; Rational decision making style, Intuitive decision making style, Dependent decision making style, Instantaneous decision making style and Avoidant decision making style (Mirmiran, 2015; p 31 quoted from Scott & Bruce, 1969).

Rational decision making style is based on evaluating all possible methods in order to getting to the best way for achieving to the goal. Intuitive decision making style is an unconscious style which is based on personal perspicacity of the manager. On the other hand the manager has no rational reason about the decision which he/she is about to take, but he leans on individual intuition and do what he / she think is true. Dependent decision making style is based on much leaning on others' information and supports. The recent method is more popular in collectivism societies. In Instantaneous decision making style; managers take decision suddenly as they confront with challenges and problems; such managers have high level of risk ability. Avoidant decision making style is the choice of managers who prolong taking decision when they confront with problems to get enough certainty. Such managers have low level of risk ability (Mirmiran, 2015; pp 34, 35 quoted from Scott & Bruce, 1969).

4.4. Culture and Decision making

The creditability of unplanned decision making style as a manuscript for decision making behavior is influenced by culture. Culture is an interactive complex of joint characteristics which influences each group interaction against environment. Since culture differs from each nation to another one; thus preferences about social, economic, environmental, public affairs differ between them (Mirmiran, 2015; pp 34, 35 quoted from Hofstede, 1978).

4.5. Zirsakht communication Co

4.5.1. Zirsakht Company History

Although the recent Zirsakht communication company follow policies and plans of the Iran government which has been codified through article 44 of the constitution policy, but it has passed the long history until getting to independency. The history has been explained in the following briefly. The Iran Telephone development company as the initial core of Zirsakht Co was established on 1989, April. Iran Telephone development Co has been named communication

Development Co. The company performance development in the communication area led to constituting a separated board of directors from Iran communication company and changing its' name to Zirsakht co.

4.5.2. Zirsakht Company International projects

Although Zirsakht is still a governmental company, but it is the ensign of developing Internet networks in Iran. Thus it has participated in many international contracts in the network communication area and many multinational project teams have been constituted during the last decade in this company.

Some of important international projects of Zirsakht Co during last five years are; the development of internet network broadband from India- Bombay to Russia- Astrakhan to the amount of 150 G B/S.

Zirsakht Co is participating in a joint cooperation with Korean KT Co in its' newest project including planning, installment and administrating fourth generation of mobile internet (4G) in Iran from 2013 till now.

The project contains three phases of planning, providing and installment of equipment & hard wares, and finalizing the project.

4.6. The Korean KT Co

4.6.1. The History of the KT Co

The KT co is the biggest communication operator in Korea that established on 1981 as a governmental corporation in Korea. KT has been merged with its' subsidiary company; Korean Telecom Freetel on 2009 and changed to the largest communication corporation in Korea. KT was awarded for the best service management in the GSL area from DJSI.

4.6.2. KT Joint Projects with Iran

Here to fore KT Company has participated in many mutual investments in the Middle East countries such as Iraq, Iran, Israel and Turkey.

KT has participated in developing of fourth generation of mobile internet (4G) in Iran since 2013 as its' newest cooperation with this country. The mentioned project costs about fifty million dollars which providing and preparing hard wares is the responsibility of KT.

4.7. Research History

4.7. 1. Foreign Research History

Here to fore of researches have been performed in the area of culture impacts on organizations performance generally and in the area of managers' performance specifically in the foreign countries which some of the most important of them have been summarized as below.

Diana Elena (2010) studied cultural differences in multi culture compares in her research with the title of "cultural differences in the project management". This research has been performed in Analez University. She has studied multinational organizations in Germany, Norway, Brazil, Canada, Japan and USA. She found that multi culture organizations show better flexibility against performance challenges in crisis situations.

Amponsah (2012) also has studied cultural reasons for project failure in organizations. He chose 200 people of project managers in Ghana accident accidentally. Questionnaires were analyzed through SPSS software. He found that cultural isotropy is an important reason for project management succession in international organizations.

Zaglago, L et al (2014) also has studied the effect of culture on implementing ERP¹ in international organizations through library studies and data analysis of the related companies. He found that ERP and culture interact with each other mutually so that culture influence on organization culture and staff culture opposition with culture may leads to ERP implementation failure.

Finally; Ansah, M (2015) in the research with the title of " the Influence of Hofstede Culture Dimension on Decision Making Procedure of Marketing Managers' which has been performed in Ghana, the researcher has investigated probable relation among marketing culture and managers' decision making styles. After analyzing questionnaires data through SPSS software he found that power Distance is significantly more than other dimensions among managers and they are better interested in conservatism.

4.7.2. Local Research History

Heretofore also some useful researches have been performed in the area of the culture role in organizations' performance; for instance Taslimi et al (2010) in their research with the title of " the Model of national culture Influence on Team Work in Iran" which was performed in Tehran university investigated the influence of national culture on team works through three social, historical and cultural aspects in the three companies in the automobile and commerce industries the number of 576 people of managers were chosen for the research the results of questionnaires is confirming Iranians' high interests to collectivism and team work .

Shoghi and Fathali (2012) have also evaluated the influence of organizational culture on the managers' leadership style and their creativity on insurance company in Markazi province. They have selected 102 people of the personnel through Available sampling method and distributed questionnaires. Questionnaires were including MLQ (Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire), Terrence questionnaire, and Denison organizational culture. Statistical analysis was made through SEM (Structural Equations Model) method. Lisrel 8.8 and smart PLS soft wares were applied for analysis. Results showed that managers' leadership style influence personnel creativity significantly. Also it was confirming the mediator role of organizational culture among leadership style and managers' creativity.

5. Research Objectives and Hypotheses

5.1. Research Objectives

5.1.1. Main Objective

- Examining the culture potential impacts on Male managers' decision making style in the project teams from Iranian and Korean nationalities.

5.1.2. Secondary objectives

- Examining potential impacts of individualism /pluralism dimension from social culture dimensions on managers' decision making style from the two Iranian and Korean nationalities.

- examining potential impacts of uncertainty from social culture dimensions on managers' decision making style from the two Iranian and Korean nationalities.

- Examining potential impacts of patriarchy/Matriarchy from the two Iranian and Korean nationalities.

1. Enterrise Resources Planning

5.2. Research Assumptions

5.2.1. Main Research Assumptions

- Social culture dimensions influence male managers' decision making styles in the project team from the two Iranian and Korean nationalities.

5.2.2. Secondary Research Assumptions

- Social culture dimensions influence male managers' decision making style in the project teams from the two Iranian and Korean nationalities.

- Individualism/ pluralism dimension from social culture dimensions influence male managers' decision making style in the project teams from the two Iranian and Korean nationalities.

- Uncertainty dimension from social culture dimensions influence male managers' decision making style in the project teams from the two Iranian and Korean nationalities.

- Matriarchy/ patriarchy dimension from social culture dimensions influence male managers' decision making style in the project teams from the two Iranian and Korean nationalities.

- There are some similarities and differences among impressibility way of Iranian and Korean managers' decision making style from social culture dimensions.

6. Research Method

Recent study is from applied research kind and it is Descriptive survey from research method aspect. At first; library studies have been performed to provide preliminary information and history for this research.

At the second step; Hofstede culture dimensions questionnaire has been applied to collect information related to social culture of participants. Also Scott and Bruce decision making style questionnaire has been applied for collecting information related to managers' decision making manner.

6.1. Statistical society

The statistical society of the recent study contains all managers who are member of project teams in the zirsakht communication co as one of the largest executive of mobile communications development plans in an international level and in relation with mobile fourth generation project in Iran on 2014.

The sample size includes the number of 300 people f managers, technical expert and administrative who are active in the project teams from the two South Korean and Iranian nationalities.

Mentioned society contains the number of 8 females and 292 of male managers including ICT experts from Iranian and Korean nationalities. Also 107 people of them are KT company personnel and 185 people of them are Zirsakhht personnel who are worming in the ICT area on 2014.

6.2. Sampling Method and Size

Since statistical society members from the two nationalities haven't work in the centralized form, therefore sampling has been performed through convenience sampling.

The sampling procedure has been accomplished as described below. At first step; the list of statistical society was prepared after Zirsakht board of director agreement. The list contained experts' cell numbers and emails. Two separated list were prepared for the two nationalities (from No; 1-185 for Iranians and 1 to 107 for Koreans).

Finally; the number of 58 of Iranians and 42 of Koreans announced their agreements for participating in the research. Due to the descriptive method of research, criteria and equality of the two society, whole available members has been chosen as sample size. Also from the total number of 300 people of the sample size; 8 persons were women and 292 people were men. Thus because of little size of female society in comparison with male society; the female society has been ignored and the research has been specified to male group.

6.3. Questionnaires

6.3.1. Hofstede Questionnaire

Hofstede localized questionnaire was applied for the managers' social culture assessment. The preliminary version of the questionnaire includes five cultural dimensions containing 22 questions. Scientific assessments referred to justifiability of the Hofstede questionnaire in relation with Iranian society concluded to eliminating 6 items from the initial version and derivation four separated elements. Also because five items of the initial questionnaire have been designed based on the two sex; the related dimension (Power Distance) was eliminated from the research and statistical society specified to males. Therefore; the localized version of Hofstede questionnaire contains 11 questions. Finally, validity of the questionnaire was confirmed through with Cronbach's coefficient alpha ($\alpha=0/7$). The answer sheet also designed based on Likert Spectrum. (1= completely agree to 5= completely disagree)

6.3.2. Scott and Bruce decision making questionnaire (1995)

The assessment of managers' decision making quality has been performed through with Scott & Bruce standard questionnaire. The mentioned questionnaire assess five decision making styles including Rational Decision Making Style, Intuitive Decision Making Style, Dependence Decision king Style, Real- time Decision Making style and Instantaneous Decision Making Style. The validity of the questionnaire has been approved through related professors and Reliability was confirmed through Cronbach's alpha ($\alpha= 0.77$).

6.3.3. Distributing Questionnaires

Questionnaires have been distributed among participants through the two methods, for the Iranian participants the researcher referred to the center branch of the Zirsakht Company in Tehran and the questionnaires were emailed to Korean participants since they weren't accessible in the face to face form at the research time.

7. Analyzing Research Data

Descriptive statistical techniques including Frequency, Percent, Average and Standard Deviation were applied for investigating and describing data relations to triple dimensions of cultural theories and data related to quintet decision making styles. Also Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) method was applied for analyzing questionnaires data for designing proposed model in connection with evaluating criteria relations and research assumptions using AMOS software Version 23. At this step; proposed model according to the research assumption was designed. Then conceptual model was designed for evaluating probable culture triple dimensions relation with quintet styles of decision making.

After that fitness indexes of the provided model including GIF², CFI³, RFI⁴, NFI⁵, NNFI⁶ and RMSEA⁷ were calculated for confirming model adaptation level. The results has been showed in the below table.

Next step was specified to designing exploratory model of the research. Fitness indexes confirmed exploratory model adaptation again.

Final step of data analysis was specified to comparing analyzed data of the two groups of participants including Pearson Correlation coefficient, T test, and calculating correlation coefficient among independent and dependent variables for the two groups.

8. Results

8.1. Research Assumptions Test Results

8.1.1. The Primary Hypothesis Results

The Primary assumption of the research is about influencing method of social culture dimensions on decision making style of male managers in the international project teams from the two Korean and Iranian nationalities.

Resulted data from evaluating exploratory model chart are showing that the impact factor average of social cultural dimensions on quintet decision making styled for the participants from the two nationalities confirms proposed assumption model.

The resulted finding are also confirming study results from Diana Elena (2010) with the title of " Study of Cultural Differences on Project Management", Amponsah (2012) with the title of " Study of Cultural Reason for Project failure" and Zaglago and et al (2014) with the title of " Study of Culture Impacts on Implementing Human Resources Management Program " and Belassi et al with the title of " the Study of Cultural Impacts on the succession of Developing Projects of New Products".

8.1.2. Sub- assumptions Results

1. Individualism- Collectivism Impacts on Decision Making Style

Data analysis refer to descriptive statistics show that correlation coefficient between Individualism/collectivism dimension and decision making styles of Dependent, Instantaneous and Intuitive are 0/343, 0/346 and 0/283 respectively which all are significant in the level of 0/01, but the results refuses the recent dimension impacts on Avoidant and Rational styles (0/149 and 0/153 respectively).

Also research exploratory model is showing that impact factor of individualism collectivism dimension on decision making styles of Dependent, Avoidant, Rational, Intuitive and instantaneous are 0/02, -0/59, 0/04, 0/00 and 0/24 respectively.

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2. Goodnes of Fit Index
 3. Comprative Fit Index
 4. Relative Fit Index
 5. Normed Fit Index
 6. Non Normed Fit Index
 7. Root Mean Square Error of Approximation

Therefore, findings confirm that individualism/ collectivism dimension doesn't influence on instantaneous style and it influence other decision making styles.

2. The impact of UAI on managers' decision making styles

Descriptive statistic data analysis show that correlation coefficient between UAI and quintet styles of decision making including Dependent, Avoidant, Rational, Instantaneous and Intuitive are 0/317, 0/465, 0/455, 0/314 and 0/493 respectively which all of them are meaningful in the 0/01 level. It is confirming that UAI influences on quintet decision making style.

On the other hand as it was mentioned in the research conceptual model; impact factor of UAI on quintet decision making styles of Dependent, Avoidant, Rational, instantaneous and intuitive are -0/37, 0/65, 0/62,-0/32 and 0/29 respectively which is confirming that UAI influence avoidant style more than others.

3. The Impact of Masculinity versus Feminity dimension on managers' decision making style.

According to data analysis results of descriptive statistics; coefficient correlation between the recent culture dimension and the quintet study of Dependent, Avoidant, Rational, instantaneous and intuitive are 0/495, 0/433, 0/425, 0/489 and 0/521 respectively which they all are significant in the 0/01.

Therefore it is found that Masculinity versus Feminity dimension influences on the quintet decision making styles.

On the other hand; as it has been mentioned in the research conceptual model styles are 0/04, 0/44, 0/42, 0/55 and 0/40 respectively. Therefore according to the recent findings Instantaneous style has been influenced maximum by this culture dimension and Rational style has been influenced minimum.

Finally the accordingly resulted data for correlation coefficient of the recent criteria in the exploratory model are 0/04, 0/44, -0/02, 0/55 and 0/40 which is confirming that the maximum impressibility refer to avoidant style and the minimum impressibility refer to rational style.

Therefore the above findings are confirming the secondary assumption 3.

4. Similarities and differences among managers in Iranian and Korean teams about the way of impressibility of their decision making styles versus social culture dimension.

Comparing results regarding to Pearson correlation coefficient between social culture dimensions and managers' decision making styles from the two Korean and Iranian nationalities is confirming the below results.

- The individualism/collectivism dimension from social culture dimensions has a negative significant impact on Dependent decision making style among Iranian managers and a positive significant impact on Korean managers.
- The individualism/collectivism dimension from social culture dimensions has a negative significant impact on Avoidant decision making style among the two groups of Iranian and Korean managers.
- The individualism/collectivism dimension from social culture dimensions has a positive significant impact on the Rational decision making style among Iranian managers and a negative significant impact among Korean managers.
- The individualism/collectivism dimension from social culture dimensions has a negative significant impact on instantaneous decision making style among Iranian managers and a positive significant impact among Korean managers.

- The individualism/collectivism dimension from social culture dimensions has a negative significant impact on Intuitive decision making style among both Iranian and Korean managers.
- the UAI (Uncertainty Avoidance Index) dimension from social culture dimensions has a negative significant on Dependent decision making style among Iranian managers and a positive significant impact among Korean managers.
- The UAI (Uncertainty Avoidance Index) dimension from social culture dimensions has a positive significant impact on Avoidant decision making style among both Iranian and Korean managers.
- The UAI (Uncertainty Avoidance Index) dimension from social culture dimensions has a positive significant impact on Rational decision making style among both Iranian and Korean managers.
- The UAI (Uncertainty Avoidance Index) dimension from social culture dimensions has a negative significant impact on Instantaneous decision making style among Iranian managers and positive significant impact among Korean.
- The UAI (Uncertainty Avoidance Index) dimension from social culture dimensions has a positive significant Impact on intuitive decision making style among both Iranian and Korean managers.
- The Masculinity versus Feminity dimension from social culture dimensions has a negative significant impact on Dependent decision making style among both Iranian and Korean managers.
- the Masculinity versus Feminity dimension from social culture dimensions has a positive significant impact on Avoidant decision making style among Iranian managers and a negative significant impact on Korean managers.
- The Masculinity versus Feminity dimension from social culture dimensions has a negative significant impact on Instantaneous decision making style among Iranian manager and positive significant on Korean managers.
- The Masculinity versus Feminity dimension from social culture dimensions has a positive significant impact on Intuitive decision making style among both Korean and Iranian managers.

9. Conclusion

The above findings is confirming that social culture influence managers' decision making style.

The finding s of the present study were compared with last researches and it was found that in the recent study impressibility of different decision making styles of two nationalities from different cultures has been explained.

The present circumstance may be useful for the administrative managers to identify and reduce their organization vulnerabilities better in the cultural differences areas and enabling them to sustain strengths in this area. For Instance; Individualism/collectivism dimension influences on Dependent decision making style; it has a negative significant on Iranian managers, but a positive significant impact on Korean managers: it means that because of being collectivism of Korean society according to Hofstede; when Individualism dimension is increased among Korean managers; the dependency in decision making will be increased, but the vector of such relation among Iranian managers is upside down although the intensity of relation is as high as the Korean managers.

Therefore in the present research; the relation kind and vector of culture dimensions with managers' favorite decision making style for the two nationalities have been explored in addition to explain culture characteristics of the target society.

Such circumstances may be helpful for the chief managers in the international organizations to forecast and prevent bias of decision making procedure by middle and subordinate managers.

Also it may be useful for the administrative managers to choose better compatible managers for the international project teams.

10. Researcher limitations

The present research has been faced with two kinds of limitations:

10.1. The researcher limitations

- Lack of accessibility to the female society for generalizing research finding o both gender.
- Lack of face to face accessibility to samples for performing interviews.
- Lack of despondence from some managers for their trips, vacations and ...etc.

10.2. Research limitations

- Since the research has been limited to males, findings are not generalize able to females necessarily.
- Since questionnaires have been sent to managers through emails, thus it may have increased bias when answering.
- Because of culture diversity among various nations; the research finding are not generalize able to other nations necessarily.

11. Suggestions

11.1. Applicable Suggestion

- It is suggested that administrative managers pay more attention to cultural compatibility when choosing international project teams' members to prevent probable contradictions in decision making procedures.
- It is necessary that administrative managers provide specific educational courses for better familiarity of managers and experts with cultural compromise to cope with cultural differences when decision making.

12. References

- [1] Amponsah, R . (2012). The Real Project Failure Factors and the Effect of Culture on Project Management in Ghana. Ghana Institute of Management and Public Administration (Gimpa).
- [2] Ansah, M. 2014. Cultural Dimension in Marketing Managers' Decision Making: An Application of Geert Hofstede Index for Ghana. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Management Sciences*, Vol. 3, No. 2
- [3] Belassi, W et al. (2013). The Impact of Organizational Culture on the Success of New Product Development Projects: A Theoretical Framework of the Missing Link. Faculty of Business, Athabasca University, Canada: pp 124-134
- [4] Bassam,H. (2013). Insights on The Impact Conformity and Commitment on Project Performance. 28th IPMA World Congress; The Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Trondheim, Norway
- [5] Debic, M et al.(2015). Cultural Differences Affecting Decision Making Style: A Comparative Study between Four Countries. *Journal of Business Economics and Management*, ISSN 1611-1699 / eISSN 2029-4433, Volume 16(2): 275-289
- [6] Elena, D.(2010). Cultural Differences in Project Management. *Annales Universitatis Apulensis Series Oeconomica*, 12(2): pp 657-664
- [7] Hofstede, G. (2011). Dimensionalizing Cultures: The Hofstede Model in Context. Universities of Maastricht and Tilburg, The Netherlands, hofstede@bart.nl
- [8] Mirmiran, F. (2014). The Study of Culture impacts on Male Managers' Decision Making within Multinational Project Teams; Case Study: Zirsakht Telecommunication Co. Thesis for Achieving MA Degree in Business Administration. Islamic Azad University, Faculty of Humanities; Department of Management Administration
- [9] Mirmiran, F. (2014). The Study of Differences between E-commerce Impacts on Developed Countries and Developing Countries; Case Study: USA and Iran. *New Marketing Research Journal*, Special Issue; PP: 79-100
- [10] Shoghi, B , Fathali, A. (2014). the influence of organizational culture on the managers' leadership style and their creativity . *Research & Scientific Journal of Insurance News*. Year 5, No 173; pp 23-45
- [11] Taslimi, S et al. (2011). The model of National Culture Influencing Model on Team Work in Iran. *Scientific & Research Journal of Culture Guideline*. No 10 , 11; pp 128- 152
- [12] Zaglago,L et al. (2014). The Impact of Culture in Enterprise Resource Planning System(ERP) Implementation. *Proceedings of the World Congress on Engineering*. WCE 2013, July 3 - 5, , London, U.K.